

Test-based virtual methods to explore NVH issues of Hybrid and Electrical Vehicles

Sacareanu Sorin¹, Irimia Cristi¹, Predica Dan ¹ and Baicoianu Alexandra ¹

¹ Siemens Industry Software, Brasov, Romania

Abstract. The paper presents authors experience on identifying, categorizing and weighting the NVH effects from important sources as Electric Motor, Wind, Tires & Road, Electronics, HVAC as well as Warning noises. The focus of this research is to use advanced Simulations and Test methods to 'shift left' the problematics of NVH in the early stage of product development using already available test data which feed performant simulation tools. The aim is to optimize the NVH performance in the context of all new car key attributes at the moment of product lifecycle when the cost is minimal.

Keywords: NVH, Simulation and Test Methods, EV, Simcenter Engineering.

1 Introduction

Electrification is here to stay. The share of hybrid and electric vehicles in the total number of vehicles sold per year is steadily increasing. According to Bloomberg New Energy Finance report [1], by 2040 it is expected to see up 50 million of new electrified vehicles sold, outnumbering the ICE vehicles sold per year as seen in Fig. 1.

All major OEMs are currently developing various architectures for hybrid and electric vehicles, therefore a huge variety of potential NVH issues may be encountered during the process. The variety of architectures makes it difficult to anticipate all the potential issues upfront and tackle them so that the vehicle performance attributes are satisfied.

The NVH sources of an EV are different that an ICE. For ICE, the main contributor is represented by the powertrain and the combustion noise. Second comes the road noise followed by road noise. Wind noise and ancillary systems like steering and wipers have a lower share to the total NVH issues. For an EV, the powertrain noise is less important, on the other hand, the road noise and wind noise are significantly increasing in importance, being the dominant ones. The ancillary proportion to the total noise is also increasing when compared to ICEs. According to [2] an additional 10% is foreseen for other noise and vibration phenomenon like warning sounds. The focus in NVH

development effort is shifting from powertrain towards road noise and aero-acoustics noise reduction.

Fig. 1. World vehicles sales by propulsion type – adapted from [1].

This paper will focus on the challenges represented by those 5 NVH sources and present the solutions offered by STS Engineering Services. Fig. 2 presents the main contributors to the total noise levels for an internal combustion engine and an electric vehicle. Analyzing into more detail, as a function of vehicle speed and frequency, an ICE vehicle noise is dominated by the structure borne noise up to 60 km/h and 400 Hz. As we go up in frequency, the air borne part of the powertrain becomes dominant. As the vehicle speed increases, the road and tire noise become more important, up to 100 Km/h. Above 100 km/h and 200 Hz, the wind noise becomes the predominant NVH factor of the total sound pressure level [2].

Fig. 2. NVH sources for ICE and EVs [2].

For an EV, the powertrain noise is significantly decreased. At speed up to 40 km/h, below 200 Hz, the ancillary systems noises are having the highest contributions to the total sound. As we move up in frequency, the electric motor is gaining some contribution, and above 2000 Hz mainly the inverter noise is encountered. As compared to an ICE, the road and tire noise dominates a broader speed range, mainly from 40 to 100 Km/h. The wind noise contribution becomes dominant even at lower speed, above 2000 Hz since we do not encounter the masking effect of an ICE air borne noise. All other components which have always been there and made noise are becoming apparent, even dominant due to the lack of masking from the ICE powertrain.

2 Electric Motor Noise

The electric powertrain is composed of the electric motor itself, the reduction gear and the power electronics. The sound pressure levels of these components are, in general, lower than what we used to encounter on the internal combustion engines, but nevertheless, their frequency, their spectral content is entirely different, the high frequency tonal components making them sound quite annoying.

The typical NVH challenges faced when developing electric vehicles are represented by integration of motor into the vehicle, controlling the sound quality rather than the level and optimizing the noise radiation. This consideration involves starting with precise noise measurements and processing these measurements in two ways:

1. **Objective Analysis:** Using defined sound quality metrics grounded in psychoacoustic science.
2. **Subjective Assessment:** Having a jury or a sample group of customers listen to the sounds to evaluate them.

The insights gained from both objective and subjective analyses can then guide the development of new, more effective metrics for future assessments or lead to design modifications aimed at enhancing sound quality. This approach highlights a significant trend: the growing importance of sound quality, focusing more on the subjective experience of drivers rather than solely on absolute noise levels.

For instance, let's consider an objective assessment comparing noise measurements between an electric vehicle (EV) and its internal combustion engine (ICE) counterpart, which are variants of the same model, presented in Fig. 3.

In the top-left figure, the overall noise levels are depicted. The green curve represents the ICE vehicle, showing typically increasing noise levels with engine speed. The blue curve, representing the electric vehicle, shows much lower noise levels, often 10 to 20 decibels quieter across most operational ranges. This indicates that electric vehicles are, in general, quieter [3].

However, the lower graph tells a different story when examining the sound quality metric known as sharpness. Here, the green curve for the ICE vehicle shows significantly lower sharpness levels compared to the higher levels seen in the electric vehicle [3]. This suggests that while electric vehicles are quieter, they do not necessarily produce a more pleasant sound. The sharpness metric highlights the potential annoyance caused by the high-frequency noises in electric cars.

Fig. 3. Comparison of noise levels between an EV and its ICE counterpart [3].

Another example involves a color map measured during a run-up of an electric car, see Fig. 3, right side. In the top graph, the traditional way of processing the data, represented in dBA, indicates sound levels. The high levels, shown in yellow and red, appear on the left side of the graph in the lower frequency range, specifically in the 200-300 Hz range [3]. Additionally, a light blue line appears, corresponding to the 48th order of the electric motor.

When people are asked in a jury test what they find annoying about this noise, they often point to that specific order [3]. This suggests that the overall level is not a good measure of annoyance. Instead, the prominence ratio, like sharpness, expresses the extent to which a particular tone stands out from the background noise. This metric correlates much better with the annoyance caused by the noise.

In Fig 3, the bottom graph, the color map clearly shows that high levels (red and yellow) occur at the frequencies and road speed ranges where the 48th order is dominant.

To summarize, subjective methods such as jury testing and listening tests, where individuals are exposed to these noises and can compare measurements from competitors, are essential. These methods help determine the appropriate metrics to express the sound quality and brand image each OEMs want to create with their electric vehicles.

In examining the design aspects alongside sound quality and target setting, we observe a structured design process, presented in Fig. 4 [3]. Initially, after the conceptual design phase, which includes the motor, power electronics, and control systems, these elements are validated using simpler 1D simulation models [7]. These models can be functional representations of the motor, consider thermal aspects, or be comprehensive enough to simulate road driving cycles, allowing for evaluations such as battery state of charge. These simulations facilitate the sizing and initial design of the motor and electric components.

As the conceptual design evolves into detailed drawings and CAD designs, the geometry data can be utilized in 3D simulations. A typical process involves conducting electromagnetic simulations. These simulations are essential not only for calculating

the performance of the electric machines but also for determining the mechanical forces associated with electromagnetic phenomena. Specifically, the electromagnetic forces between the rotor and the stator are calculated [6].

These forces are then applied to a vibro-acoustic model, initially a structural model, to predict the vibrations of the stator under these electromagnetic forces. Consequently, this allows us to predict the acoustic sound pressure or sound power radiated by the electric motor. This methodology enables accurate predictions of noise levels generated by electric motors.

Finally, once the powertrain is designed and integrated into a vehicle, validation and, if necessary, troubleshooting is conducted. This involves testing the full vehicle, for instance, on a chassis dynamometer or on the road. In addition to traditional measurements of vibrations and sound pressure levels, we also recommend measuring electrical phenomena such as the current in different motor phases.

Thus, the design process progresses from 1D simulations, through 3D simulations, to physical testing.

Fig. 4. Structured design process of an EV [3,6].

3 Wind Noise

Wind noise is not new or specific to electric cars; it has been a concern for traditional cars as well. However, as highlighted in the introduction, the absence of a combustion engine in electric vehicles eliminates the low-frequency masking effects, making wind noise a more prominent issue even at lower speeds. Traditionally, wind noise became significant at speeds of 100 to 150 km/h, which are not typically dominant in daily usage. For an EV, wind noise can become a significant concern even at lower speeds.

There are challenges related to both testing and simulation of wind noise. Traditional wind noise testing in wind tunnels is expensive, limiting the number of feasible tests. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct these tests as efficiently as possible, minimizing the number of iterations.

At Simcenter Engineering, we aim to invest in equipment that enhances the efficiency of these measurements. Wind tunnel instrumentation typically includes in-vehicle instruments such as a binaural head for sound quality measurements and an acoustic 3D camera to identify noise sources on the body panels. We also recommend measurements on the infrastructure, such as the turntable where the car is positioned or a traverse robot that can move around the vehicle [4].

Most importantly, we believe valuable insights can be gained from extensive microphone arrays placed outside the flow, at a distance from the vehicle on the sides, top, and front.

In addition to testing, simulation plays a crucial role because, as mentioned, testing is and remains expensive. We aim to reduce testing to the bare minimum and make it as efficient as possible. One effective way to achieve this is through simulation. For example, using STAR-CCM+ codes can accurately predict flow phenomena, such as the air flow behind the side mirror or the pressure exerted by these turbulences on exterior surfaces like the side door glass.

Fig. 5 illustrates this process, where the simulation helps in understanding these complex interactions. Moreover, the simulation enables the transfer of this data to practical applications, allowing for adjustments and optimizations in the design phase without the need for extensive physical testing [4].

Fig. 5. Using STAR-CCM+ and SimCenter to determine the Wind Noise [4].

By leveraging advanced simulation tools, we can gain detailed insights into wind noise behavior and its impact on vehicle acoustics. This approach not only reduces the reliance on expensive wind tunnel tests but also enhances the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the design and development process.

When considering testing versus simulation, it is essential to weigh the advantages and disadvantages of each approach. As previously mentioned, testing can be expensive, primarily due to the cost of wind tunnel time, and it requires hardware to be available. However, once a testing setup is operational, especially with advanced tools like highly instrumented acoustic arrays in wind tunnels, it becomes possible to measure numerous configurations in a relatively short period.

On the other hand, simulations offer the advantage of exploring multiple scenarios upfront without the need for physical prototypes. This upfront exploration can significantly reduce the amount of testing required later in the development process. However, simulations can be computationally intensive, particularly in the high-frequency range, posing challenges in terms of computation time.

Our approach emphasizes the integration of testing and simulation wherever possible. By leveraging simulation to address as many issues as possible upfront, we can mitigate the need for extensive testing. Additionally, we advocate for investing in measures that optimize testing efficiency, ensuring that the tests that remain necessary are conducted in the most efficient manner possible.

4 Road Noise

Road noise, like wind noise, is not exclusive to electric vehicles but has been a longstanding concern in automotive engineering. As mentioned in the introduction, the absence of low-frequency masking from combustion engines has accentuated the prominence of road noise, particularly at lower speeds, where it becomes the dominant noise source.

Road noise comprises two main components: tire noise and structure-borne noise. Tire noise arises from the interaction between the tire pattern and the road surface and is predominantly transmitted through the air. On the other hand, structure-borne noise, often termed "road noise," stems from the suspension system being excited by road irregularities, which is then transferred to the vehicle body through the suspension links.

The optimal approach to addressing road noise involves a combination of testing and simulation as seen in Fig. 6. For example, in road noise simulations, we integrate testing and simulation models to achieve comprehensive results. For suspension optimization, we typically utilize test-based models for tire and vehicle body, along with either test or simulation-based descriptions of the mounts. Additionally, simulation models of subframes or suspension links are incorporated into the hybrid assembly.

Fig. 6. Hybrid Test/FE approach [3].

This hybrid approach, blending testing and simulation, enables a thorough understanding of road noise phenomena and facilitates effective optimization strategies.

Loads, whether obtained from testing or simulation, provide valuable data for optimizing vehicle structures and mounts to mitigate road noise. These loads may include road surface data or wheel spindle load data, which, when analyzed, offer insights into potential modifications to enhance the interaction between components and optimize road noise. Machine learning algorithms can be used for condition monitoring of vehicle suspension components [5].

Identifying the root cause of road noise and understanding the impact of modifications on interior noise levels are achievable through simulation models. However, it's essential to note that components within these simulation models often rely on actual test data from predecessors or separate components.

By leveraging a combination of test data and simulation models, engineers can accurately predict the effects of structural changes on road noise attenuation. This integrated approach enables informed decision-making in optimizing vehicle design to achieve desired noise reduction goals.

5 Ancillary Systems

This section will consider ancillary systems, which are emerging as significant noise sources that demand our attention as engineers. While some of these noise sources are indeed new, many are not. Components such as the cooling system, HVAC, steering systems, and wipers have always existed in traditional cars. However, they were often unnoticed or sufficiently refined to remain inconspicuous due to the masking effect of the combustion engine. With this masking effect now absent, these sounds have become more noticeable and, consequently, more annoying.

Addressing NVH (Noise, Vibration, and Harshness) issues in these components has become imperative. Given the wide variety of ancillary components, the paper will focus on a few examples to illustrate the challenges and solutions.

One notable example is the electric power steering (EPS) system optimization process presented in Fig.7. For the EPS NVH optimization, starting by modeling the system using functional 1D models, will facilitate the sizing of components and the development of control systems.

Fig. 7. Multi domain engineering supporting all aspects of EPS development [3].

These models help derive load cases, whether in the rack and pinion or within the power steering system itself. The load cases then lead to the creation of prototypes, which can be evaluated on testing rigs. For instance, the steering rig shown in Fig. 7 allows for the actuation of the steering wheel rotationally and the tie rods laterally, enabling comprehensive assessment of the EPS performance and its associated noise characteristics.

The prototype physical model can then be validated as a system on a test rig. By assembling it in the vehicle other aspects can be measured and validated: system integration or coupling effects.

The second example involves HVAC systems, which are particularly complex from an NVH perspective. There are two main aspects to consider. First, the airflow within the tubes, driven by fans through vents and ducts, generates turbulence and acoustic sound pressure variations.

The process recommended by Simcenter Engineering is presented in Fig. 8. It begins with a flow simulation using computational fluid dynamics (CFD), using Star-CCM+. The results of this flow simulation serve as inputs for an acoustic simulation using Simcenter 3D acoustics. This approach allows us to accurately predict the sound pressure generated by the airflow in the ducts at the driver's ear location.

Fig. 8. HVAC NVH development process [3, 4].

6 Warning Sounds

Another type of sound specific to EVs is represented by the pedestrian warning systems. Legislation is either already in place or forthcoming to address the issue of electric vehicles being exceptionally quiet, especially at low speeds, which poses a risk to vulnerable road users who might not hear them approaching, leading to dangerous situations [8].

Extensive studies have been conducted by various legislative and regulatory organizations, as well as by associations representing visually impaired individuals. These

studies unanimously indicate that the quiet nature of electric vehicles indeed increases the risk of accidents involving vulnerable road users.

As a result, legislation prescribing minimum noise levels for electric vehicles is already in effect in the EU and US [8,9]. This necessitates the development of testing methods to ensure compliance. Simcenter Engineering has developed enhancements to the pass-by noise testing software, traditionally used to measure and ensure that vehicles do not exceed maximum noise limits. This software can now also assess minimum noise requirements for electric vehicles, applicable both in controlled indoor environments and outdoor settings, see Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Test based methods for assessing the pedestrian warning noise [10].

Additionally, significant efforts are being made in the simulation of these systems. We participated in a European project called eVADER, aimed at designing and studying pedestrian warning systems. Using Simcenter acoustic solutions, we developed simulation procedures that start with a loudspeaker input as a source to accurately simulate the directivity and noise levels perceived by pedestrians at various locations around the vehicle [10].

7 Conclusions

In summary, the paper has highlighted several issues that are either new or have gained significance with the transition from combustion engines to electric vehicles.

The transition from combustion engines to electric vehicles has introduced a range of new challenges and highlighted existing ones, particularly in the areas of sound quality of electric powertrains, wind noise, road noise, ancillary system noise, and pedestrian safety. Addressing these issues effectively requires a synergistic approach that combines both testing and simulation. Our Simcenter tools and services exemplify this integrated methodology, enabling accurate predictions, efficient testing, and troubleshooting. Based on the described methods, optimal design adjustments can be done that will help to enhance the overall performance and safety of electric vehicles.

Acknowledgments. This work is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101079242 – HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

References

1. Bloomberg NEF (2024, May 20) “**Electric Vehicle Outlook 2023**”, <https://about.bnef.com/electric-vehicle-outlook/>
2. Goetchius, Gregory M.. “**Leading the Charge -The Future of Electric Vehicle Noise Control**.” *Sound and Vibration* 45 (2011): 5-8 DOI:10.32604.
3. Siemens Digital Industries Software (2024, May 19) “**Address NVH Engineering issues of Hybrid and Electric Vehicles**” – Webinar, <https://webinars.sw.siemens.com/en-US/nvh-engineering-for-hybrid-and-electric-vehicles/>
4. Siemens PLM Automation (2024, May 20) “**Essentials of vehicle aero-acoustics testing**” – Webinar, https://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/media/global/pt/5_wind-tunnel-testing_Webinar-65791_tcm70-11058.pdf
5. Baicoianu, A., Stanoiu, P., Velea, M., Husar, C.: “**A Machine Learning Proposal for Condition Monitoring of Vehicle Suspension**”, 2022 International Conference on INnovations in Intelligent SysTems and Applications (INISTA), Biarritz, France, DOI: 10.1109/INISTA55318.2022.9894160 (2022)
6. Raia, R., Ruba, M., Martis, C., Husar, C., Sirbu, G.M.: “**Battery electric vehicle (BEV) powertrain modelling and testing for real-time control prototyping platform integration**”, 23rd European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE'21 ECCE Europe) DOI: 10.23919/EPE21ECCEurope50061.2021.9570616 (2021)
7. C. Irimia, M. Grovu, G. Sirbu, A. Birtas, C. Husar, M. Ponchant, “**The modeling and simulation of an Electric Vehicle based on Simcenter Amesim platform**”, 2019 Electric Vehicles International Conference & Show (EVSHOW'19), Bucharest, Romania, 2019 DOI: 10.1109/EV.2019.8892901
8. European Commission Press Release (2014-04-02). “**Commission welcomes Parliament vote on decreasing vehicle noise**”. European Commission. Archived from the original on 2014-04-07. Retrieved 2014-04-0
9. PR Newswire (2023, Jan 20) “**Critical Pedestrian Safety Legislation Moves to White House for President’s Signature**” <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/critical-pedestrian-safety-legislation-moves-to-white-house-for-presidents-signature-112016879.html>
10. Siemens Digital Industries Software (2024, May, 3), “**Acoustic vehicle alerting system**”, white paper, https://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/media/global/ja/SiemensSW-Acoustic-vehicle-alerting-system_WhitePaper_tcm57-76714.pdf